

Tourism and Neurodiversity: A Problematisation and Research Agenda

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Abstract

This paper contributes to tourism knowledge by critically analysing the social model of disability as it applies to neurodiversity. It concludes that neurodiversity is poorly problematised within tourism literature. Thus, while the social model has been widely adopted by the industry and governments, it lacks the potency required to challenge the focus of industry providers on serving the needs of neurotypical holidaymakers. The model fails to identify what changes are required and who should have responsibility for implementing them. The paper further applies the social model to a particular example of neurodiversity – the challenges involved in holidaymaking for families with autistic children– and develops a framework for action with three tiers of responsibility (governments, the tourism system, neurodiverse families). Finally, the paper identifies a research agenda for the future study of tourism and neurodiversity with particular reference to the responsibilities of the tourism industry, tourists and governments (including charitable organisations).

Keywords: neurodiversity, family holidays, autism, responsibilities, tourism management, research agenda

Introduction

The tourism literature has tended to implicitly assume that tourists are ‘neurotypical’ rather than ‘neurodivergent’. The term ‘neurodivergent’ is a neologism that refers to people who have neurological development *conditions* such as autism, attention deficit (hyperactivity) disorder (AD(H)D), Tourette’s syndrome and dyspraxia. People who are neurodivergent experience the

world in different ways to ‘neurotypical’ people. This includes their motivations, needs and experiences related to tourism. Despite its growing size and market value, however, this customer group tends to go unrecognised both by academia and tourism industry professionals.

This paper considers the implications of neurodiversity for tourism, focusing particularly on holidaymaking by ‘neurodiverse’ families, defined here as including one or more neurodivergent child. For most families, taking a holiday provides an opportunity to spend quality time together, bond as a family group and make happy memories (Backer & Schänzel, 2012; Gram, 2005). For neurodiverse families, holidays often assume an even greater importance given that they have the potential to provide them with respite from their home lives, which are typically complex and stressful for all family members. Family holidays can, however, also be stressful times that need to be negotiated especially carefully by the neurodiverse family (Amet, 2013; Jepson et al., 2022; Sedgley et al., 2017). This paper therefore sets out first to review the concept of neurodiversity through the lens of the social model of disability. The paper highlights that while the social model is not universally accepted as an alternative to the traditional ‘medical’ model, its increased acceptance has stimulated a growth in academic literature, largely outside of the tourism field. It is argued, however, that the social model of disability lacks potency as a means of addressing the challenges neurodiverse families typically face in taking holidays together. This is because applying the model may provide a better understanding of the challenges, but it does not provide a well-developed agenda for addressing them. This means that the social model does not effectively problematise the challenges of tourism on the part of neurodiverse families.

The current lack of support within the tourism industry with respect to recognising and meeting the needs and wants of neurodivergent people can also be seen to be in conflict with the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by not offering inclusive products and services to reduce inequality (SDG 10), and thus denying people opportunities to ensure their lives are

healthy through opportunities (such as holidays) to enhance their well-being (SDG 3). With the aim of remedying this situation, the paper proceeds to identify a range of challenges associated with tourism by neurodiverse families. Focusing on families with autistic children, the paper then applies the social model of disability to identify potential means of addressing such challenges and, in particular, to consider who can and should take responsibility for enabling and enacting them. This, in turn, allows a research agenda for neurodiversity in tourism to be drawn up. It can be argued that pursuing such an agenda not only makes good business sense for tourism industry organisations of all kinds but is also important in terms of society's aspirations to achieve greater social inclusion. This paper therefore maintains that new industry practices are required to help neurodivergent families exercise their human rights and benefit from family holidays in the same ways as neurotypical families do (Hamed, 2013). There remains, however, an important gap in knowledge with regard to understanding and praxis in this area.

Before proceeding it is important to identify the positionality of the authors. All three are neurotypical but two authors are parents of autistic children, and all have worked closely with autistic charities in order to gain deeper perspectives of the complexities associated with autism and to ensure that research with autistic communities is both ethical and compassionate at all times.

Neurodiversity

A central argument of this paper is that tourism theory and practice tend to favour the neurotypical holidaymaker. Accordingly, a brief review of the notion of neurodiversity is warranted. The present section therefore presents an overview of the notion of neurodiversity

and its theorisation. This paves the way for the remainder of this paper to present a problematisation of neurodiversity in the specific context of family tourism.

The use of the term 'neurodiversity' is relatively new among scholars. Harmon (2004) traces its origins to autistic interest groups in the US in the 1990s, who demanded that autistic people not be stereotyped as disabled or 'abnormal', but be considered diverse and different, and treated with the same respect as everyone else. In the UK, the study of neurodiversity began predominantly with Mary Colley (to whom this paper is dedicated): an educator, humanitarian, and visionary. Colley founded the Developmental Adult Neuro-Diversity Association (DANDA) in 2003 and was the first researcher to recognise the behavioural overlaps between conditions like autism (including Asperger's syndrome), developmental coordination disorder (DCD, also known as dyspraxia), Tourette's syndrome, dyslexia, dyscalculia, and attention deficit (hyperactivity) disorder (AD(H)D). There is a dearth with respect to statistical data and understanding of the prevalence of neurodiversity worldwide, as most countries report on neurodiverse conditions separately. ADHD for example is thought to have a 5% prevalence worldwide (Catalá-López et al., 2017), with the exception of the US (8.4% of children 2-17 years of age) (Danielson et al., 2018). DCD is thought to have up to 6% prevalence worldwide (Quinn, 2005), and dyslexia up to 10% prevalence worldwide (Blank et al., 2019). Some countries have begun to collate statistics: in the UK for example, it is estimated that around one in 10 people is neurodivergent (Autistica, 2019).

Figure 1 provides an overview of the concept of neurodiversity, the conditions it embraces, and the traits associated with those conditions that are generally considered to be negative by society.

Figure 1. Neurodiversity and neurodivergent conditions

Source: Adapted by the authors from Dyslexia Scotland (2020)

Figure 1 Alt text: The figure displays the types of neurodivergent conditions, and these include developmental co-ordination disorder (DCD), autism, dyscalculia, tourettes, dyslexia, attention deficit (hyperactivity) disorder (AD(H)HD). The figure demonstrates that the different conditions are not isolated and a neurodiverse person could have more than one interrelated condition with both strengths and difficulties.

It is important to recognise that many neurodivergent people have more than one neurodiverse condition. A recent study of 407 children with neurological conditions by Hansen et al. (2018), for example, found that 21.7% had more than one neurodiverse condition. This tendency for conditions to cross over, often sharing similar behavioural traits, can confound the specific diagnosis of particular neurological conditions, making it more difficult to meet the

neurodivergent person’s needs and wants. Co-morbidities are also common amongst neurodiverse populations. These co-occurring conditions are not necessarily related to the neurodiverse condition itself but may be more manifest when the individual concerned is neurodivergent. For example, while anxiety is not a condition necessarily associated with autism, a person with autism may have elevated levels of anxiety when they are persistently exposed to sensory overload. Indeed, the study by Hansen et al. (2018) found that 58% of participants had psychiatric conditions, anxiety being the most frequent. These traits and comorbidities manifest as everyday complexities and challenges to children and their families, which are often magnified while on holiday when neurodivergent children are placed in contexts that disadvantage them.

Current understandings of neurodiversity are informed by two ways of thinking about neurological differences: the medical model and the social model. These models are used to frame neurodiversity as a phenomenon, which in turn explains how society views and acts with respect to neurodiversity. A better understanding of the differences between the two models will allow tourism researchers to position themselves in relation to the context of their study. The following discussion illustrates the main points of opposition in the two models, as summarised in Table 1.

Medical Model of Neurodiversity	Social Model of Neurodiversity
A collection of neurological disorders/divergences from what is considered normal	A collection of conditions that imply a different way of existing from what is typical
Views people as patients: Individual diagnosis and/or treatment to remove or remediate the associated problems	Views neurodiversity as socially constructed: Changes are needed in societal attitude, acceptance and support, removal of barriers, provision of inclusive environments
Views disorders as individual impairments that present challenges to the individual	Recognises that differences are not necessarily disadvantages
Disorders are detached from a patient's identity and need to be treated within medical practice	Neurodiversity is part of a person's individual personality and should be celebrated and not

	hidden
Disorders are quantified/assessed in terms of severity (e.g., the ‘autism spectrum’)	Severity is seen as an unrealistic and unhelpful way of classifying differences
Ethics of care: Viewed as entitlement to individual medical treatment and to be treated with dignity and respect by medical professionals	Human rights: The right to be treated in every way as equal to neurotypicals and to not suffer from discrimination/marginalisation

Table 1. Points of oppositionality in the medical and social models of neurodiversity (Authors’ own, from Oliver, 2013; Ripamonti, 2016; Chapman, 2019; Loo et al., 2021; Nelson, 2021)

Table 1 Alt text: "Medical Model" of Neurodiversity is different and oppositional to the "social model" – for example the medical model - patients have individual problems but in opposition the social model - society is the problem as it is inflexible to neurodiverse needs.

From a medical model perspective, neurodiversity is seen as a collection of neurological disorders. The ontological foundations of the medical model are derived from medical science and assume that there is a ‘normal’ state of human neurological functioning, and that any divergence can only be recognised by means of individual diagnosis (Loo et al., 2021). The medical model treats people who have neurodiverse conditions as patients or ‘sufferers’ of an impairment that can only be overcome through individual medical intervention. Such intervention could be in the form of medication to attempt to cure the condition or relieve some or all of its symptoms. Alternatively, it could involve the provision of medical technology to assist the individual in overcoming their impairments.

The medical model of disability is increasingly becoming viewed as inferior to the social model, not only in its application to disability in general but also with regard to neurodiversity specifically. There are a number of reasons for this. First, the framing of neurodivergent conditions as disorders under the medical model identifies only the impairments associated

with neurodiversity and largely ignores the positive attributes. As Nelson (2021) suggests, this provides an incomplete perspective of neurodiversity by focusing on what neurodivergent people cannot do in comparison to neurotypical people. The social model, in contrast, maintains that being neurodiverse is just a different expression of human existence (Jaarsma & Welin, 2012), involving different ways of sensing, communicating, and socialising. It is increasingly being recognised, moreover, that these differences are not necessarily a disadvantage to the individual (Ortega, 2009) but are alternate and acceptable forms of human neurology (Wolbring, 2007). The differences may even be seen as an advantage to the individual expressing them. The social model problematises neurodiversity not as an individual medical condition but as a phenomenon that is socially constructed. A distinction is thus drawn between individual impairment and social disablement (Chapman, 2019). This means the lack of equality for neurodivergent people can only be addressed through the exercise of a combination of both individual and collective responsibility, social action and integration, and environmental manipulation (such as accessible building design). It also requires action with regard to the broader political and human rights agenda, the aim being to change people's attitudes and understanding of neurodiversity, which currently serves as a constraint to the development of equality. The role of governments, the third sector, NGOs and charities is paramount in this, as they can inform and advise on the issue and help develop appropriate legislation, policy and guidance. In the UK, the Department of Health and Social Care and Department for Education's (2021) *National strategy for autistic children, young people and adults: 2021 to 2026* is an important first step in this, but future research into appropriate guidance and relevant policy for the tourism sector is needed.

A second problematic feature of the medical model of disability is that it views neurodiverse conditions as detached from a patient's identity and not a contributing factor to their personality or strengths. It therefore suppresses neurodivergent people's authentic personalities and

development of self: aspects of neurodiverse conditions should be treated, masked or suppressed (Ripamonti, 2016). The medical model supports the understanding that there is a range of medical conditions that may overlap or co-occur with neurodivergence, such as anxiety or other developmental needs, but it tends to treat these aspects as separate conditions rather than view them as connected (Doyle, 2020). The social model, in contrast, views any neurological differences and groups of secondary conditions as connected and as these together forming a key part of a neurodivergent person's identity (Chapman, 2019).

Thirdly, there is also oppositionality to how neurodiversity is diagnosed. The medical model seeks to quantify or assess neurodiverse conditions in respect of the severity or intensity of the condition(s), as evidenced by the notion of the 'autism spectrum'. The social model, however, views neurodiversity as a cluster of conditions and argues that the severity of conditions is an unrealistic way to classify neurological differences. The medical model views neurodiversity from an individual rights perspective: e.g., how patients are best treated with dignity and respect within the ethics of care or duty of care provided by medical professionals. From a social model perspective, however, the focus is upon collective human rights, which are defined by the UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) (2017, n.p.) as "inherent to all human beings, regardless of class, nationality, sex, ethnicity, religion, or any other status". By virtue of being a member of the human race alone, all human beings should be equally entitled to certain rights and protections without discrimination. Fundamentally, human rights are intended to encourage the core principles of equality, non-discrimination, participation and inclusion, which could act as a bridge to societal change and thus to achieving the UN SDGs. This, of course, raises the issue of who takes responsibility to ensure this happens. Under the medical model, responsibility is vested in the healthcare professionals to

care for and treat neurodivergent patients; under the social model, responsibilities are shared among all members of society.

The social model has, meanwhile, attracted the criticism that it fails to account for differences in race, gender, sexuality and age, and presents neurodiverse people as one homogenous group (Oliver, 2013). It also strongly implies that personal impairments are not the problem, but society is (Barnes, 2019; Shakespeare, 2006). By extending the root of the problem to society as a whole, however, there is danger that its efficacy may be diluted. As the saying goes, when something is everybody's job, it becomes nobody's job.

Overview of Research on Tourism and Neurodiversity

The tourism literature has by no means ignored disability issues. A considerable literature already exists that attempts to link the issues of accessibility, disability and inclusivity in the tourism context. The tourism literature has, however, tended to focus on physical disabilities (e.g., Darcy et al., 2020; Eichhorn et al., 2013; Poria et al., 2010; Small et al., 2012; Tutuncu & Lieberman, 2016). There have also been calls for tourism to be designed to be inclusive of the needs and wants of both disabled and non-disabled people (Gillovic & MacIntosh, 2020), although such discussion often implicitly assumes that the disabled people are neurotypical. Very few researchers have engaged specifically with tourism and neurodiversity.

The preferences and behaviours of neurodivergent tourists are still, therefore, poorly understood. A recent report on family holidays with autistic children, for example, suggested that many families with autistic children prefer more frequent, shorter, domestic holidays over one main, longer, international holiday. This was found mainly to be a result to the complexities and challenges such families face when going on a holiday, including changes in an autistic

child's routine, social interaction challenges, and a lack of awareness, empathy, understanding or support for children with autism from other holidaymakers (Stadler et al, 2021). Freund et al.'s (2019) study identified the wide heterogeneity of autistic travellers when booking accessible accommodation. They found a relationship between the intrinsic constraints experienced by the family (such as lack of money or lack of time) and the intention to take a family holiday. The findings also suggested that those families whose children had 'more severe' autism were less likely to travel. This is a controversial finding insofar as there are presently no formal means or 'tools' for measuring the 'severity' of autism, and many individuals and organisations prefer not to adopt such terminology (McConachie et al., 2015).

Sedgley et al.'s (2017) more comprehensive analysis into the experiences of mothers taking holidays with their autistic sons is also important within the field of tourism, as it begins to critique the idealistic and homogenous nature of holiday products aimed at neurotypical families, while unpacking the complexities experienced and associated with autistic children and their families on holiday. However, the support and provision for neurodiverse families remains fragmented, infrequent, and biased towards neurotypical products and services.

Further research on neurodiversity in the specific context of tourism is extremely limited. Dattolo et al. (2016), for example, developed and tested a set of guidelines to help tourism websites become more friendly to autistic users, while Cena et al. (2020) developed an autism-friendly tour guidebook for heritage attractions.

Challenges for holidaymaking by families with autistic children

It must be recognised that each neurodivergent child, each family and each family holiday is a unique case, and that the challenges faced by neurodiverse families in taking holidays and the means by which they might best be addressed are therefore multiple and highly complex. It is not possible to consider them all within the confines of a single research paper such as this. To reduce the scope of the research to a workable level, this section of the paper will explore autism as an instructive example of neurodiversity. Even then, it is important to be aware that there is substantial heterogeneity in the experiences of those with this condition, which is further complicated by the wide range of additional medical conditions that tend to accompany autism (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Autism core symptoms, neurological, systemic issues and related disorders

Source: Adapted by the authors from Rodríguez and Escalona (2018).

Figure 2 Alt text: Autism has core symptoms and related disorders. Core symptoms: language impairment, social deficits, repetitive behaviours. Associated neurological issues: sleep deficits, moods, anxiety, seizures, hyperactivity, attention. Related disorders: ADHD, OCD, sleep disorders, mood disorders, anxiety disorders. Associated systemic issues: GI disorders, anxiety dysfunction.

Autism was first recorded by physicians in the 18th century as a specific difference related to eye contact and social communication, as well as a general learning disability characterised by limited 'normal' social functions (Wolff, 2004). In the absence of a biomedical explanation, the 'refrigerator mother' hypothesis was proposed by Bruno Bettelheim in the 1940s (Kanner, 1968). This hypothesis argued that autism in children was effectively the result of bad parenting in the form of mothers who were unable to have warm and supportive emotional relationships with their children. Later, autism was considered to be a 'schizophrenia of childhood', characterised by extreme detachment from reality (Evans, 2013). Wolff (2004) goes on to explain that Asperger's syndrome was originally used to differentiate between high- and low-functioning individuals, with individuals who have Asperger's syndrome being considered on the high end. This understanding was replaced by the establishment of an 'autistic spectrum', of which Asperger's syndrome is simply one variant (Wing & Gould, 1979). The 'spectrum' has many critics especially in the autistic community as it 'labels/ categorises' and therefore attaches and reinforces stigma through a continued medicalisation of the condition. Autism is idiopathic, meaning that no known cause or trigger can be identified or linked to its diagnosis (Autism Speaks, 2010, cited in Hamed, 2013). Autism occurs in all societies, irrespective of gender, ethnicity or socio-economic status. It has been known for some time, however, that autism prevalence is much higher among boys than girls (Autism Speaks, 2010; National Autistic Society, 2022a). There is however much debate as to the accuracy of statistics on

prevalence. This is due to recent research findings suggesting that girls are much better at hiding, camouflaging or ‘masking’ their autism than boys (Wood-Downie et al., 2021).

Further evidence also suggests that late diagnosis has been associated with increased mental health difficulties (Hull et al., 2019; Lai & Baron-Cohen, 2015) and as a risk marker for suicidality (Cassidy et al., 2018). Population-based estimates of autism prevalence vary greatly, from 5.1 to 15.5 per thousand births (Bourke et al., 2016). The World Health Organization (WHO) indicates that one in 160 children worldwide are autistic (between 1% and 1.6% of the world’s population), (WHO, 2021). Many observers do, however, question the reliability of these and other figures on the prevalence of autism, as it is not known how many children are living without a diagnosis and are, as Wharmby (2018, n.p.) indicates, “desperately trying to live their life in a world not designed for them” but for neurotypicals.

Holidays can be an important time for the personal development of autistic children, as well as other family members and, indeed, for the family entity (Sedgley et al., 2017). Holidays can also provide important new learning opportunities for autistic children (García-Villamizar & Dattilo, 2010; Walton, 2019). Urry (1996) further suggests that holidays are consumed as a form of escapism because they “generate pleasurable experiences which are different from those typically encountered in everyday life” (p. 1). Neurodiverse families arguably have complicated, challenging and difficult home lives, so they have much to escape from (Amet, 2013). Such holiday experiences tend however, to come with a range of complexities and challenges for families with autistic children.

More specifically, Stadler et al. (2021) suggest that the challenges faced by autistic children while on holiday are often multiple, complex and far reaching. These impacts can be experienced by the child(ren) themselves, their parents/carers and their siblings – indeed, by the whole family corporately. Hypersensitivity and sensory demands, repetitive and/or stereotyped behavioural patterns, communication and social interaction challenges, sleeping, rest patterns and other medical problems, are all additional challenges a neurodiverse family may face with little to no support available when on holiday. Indeed, it is the fact that families are left to manage the complexities themselves and the lack of understanding from other holidaymakers, accommodation providers, staff and others, that many report to be the biggest challenge of all. One survey respondent, a single parent, noted that she needs “a holiday myself by the time I get back having my son full time on my own!” (Stadler et al, 2021, p. 19).

To illustrate some of the specific challenges, for example, if an autistic person becomes emotionally overwhelmed by an experience, they may employ a range of coping mechanisms, including repetitive or stereotypical behaviours (Armstrong, 2010; Robertson, 2010). Dempsey et al. (2021) investigated air travel experiences with autistic children and young adults and identified that periods of waiting, crowds, and sensory stimuli were common stressors and potential causes of stimming. Self-stimulation or ‘stimming’, can include repeatedly flapping arms, flicking fingers, grinding teeth, walking on toes, rocking back and forth while sitting, and lining up everyday objects in a particular way (Edelson, 2012). These movements and actions are a calming mechanism for autistic people, as they are able to control these movements and therefore feel they have at least some agency in the situation. In the context of family holidays, there is the possibility that repetitive behaviour and stimming will increase as the autistic child experiences a range of emotions brought about through exposure to various parts of the tourism system, and because the familiar environment of home is replaced by that of a changing holiday environment (Sedgley et al., 2017). A new bedroom and bed, changes in

mealtimes, unfamiliar food, unfamiliar climate or weather, a constantly changing holiday environment, and different sleep patterns, can all be difficult for an autistic child who needs consistency and routine. Stadler et al. (2021) note that the onus is typically on the parents to address these challenges, for example by accompanying a child who is pacing around a property because they feel unsettled and cannot sleep.

An autistic child may also struggle to understand social cues, gestures, facial expressions, or the concept of personal space (Gessaroli et al., 2013). The complexity of social interaction will likely be greater during the holiday, as holidays inevitably involve more-frequent interaction with strangers, who will naturally be expecting neurotypical social interactions. Perhaps unsurprisingly, the most important consideration for families with an autistic child when planning a holiday is finding a peaceful/ quiet, and uncrowded location (Burrow, 2022). Many activities advertised as part of a holiday will also be designed for neurotypicals, including children's clubs and leisure facilities such as swimming pools, and autistic children may not take well to these. With this lack of activities available that suit a neurodiverse family's needs, it is again down to the parents to find alternative options.

Due to the lack of support available, these and other challenges faced by autistic children can potentially have a detrimental impact upon the whole family. An often-overlooked issue is the impact this may have on other siblings, in terms of the perception of the unfair or uneven treatment of siblings, and family conflict as a result of this, as well as the need for effective coping strategies on the part of the siblings (Bancroft, 2018). Holidays are often associated with the balancing and restoration of equilibrium, although in a family with both neurotypical and autistic children achieving this balance represents an additional challenge for the family as a whole. Hamed (2013) hence concluded that "tourism is one of [the] services that need to be restructured or re-organised with all its components, transportation, accommodation,

sightseeing, recreation and other tourist activities, to suit and meet the autistic tourist's needs and desires" (p. 4). Although this study opened up the discourse into tourism and neurodiversity, very few papers provide specific recommendations for the tourism industry. Neo and Flaherty (2018) provide an exception as they very briefly describe some of the challenges faced by autistic travellers and the responses the tourism industry has made, such as quiet rooms at airports.

The above analysis and synthesis of literature highlights that tourism providers currently do not make enough adjustments; nor do they provide adequate support for neurodiverse families. Future research is thus needed at the tourism system level of responsibility for creating new contributions to knowledge and developing best practices that help neurodiverse families enjoy their holidays in the same way as neurotypical families do.

Tourism management responses and future research

Neurodiverse families are currently expected to manage the many challenges of holidaymaking themselves. Drawing upon the social model of neurodiversity and the UN SDGs, a core argument of this paper is that this cannot be the sole responsibility of families, but rather that all actors need to take responsibility for the changes they can most effectively make. While it is agreed by most tourism researchers that the adoption of the social model is a huge step forward, it often lacks the means through which to be implemented, and responsibilities are not always clear. The problems identified in this paper also show that there is currently a lack of understanding of what these responsibilities might include and how they can contribute to positive holiday experiences for neurodiverse families.

Figure 3 therefore highlights the current gaps in knowledge across three main levels of responsibility – governments, the tourism system, and families – and outlines their different roles in providing positive holiday experiences for families with neurodivergent children. The three levels are inter-related, and it is therefore argued that change can only be achieved if stakeholders at each level recognise and take responsibility for neurodiversity in their different roles: (1) at the government level, developing a better understanding and awareness of neurodiversity is required, for example through appropriate legislation, policy and guidance. This includes working with the third sector, NGOs and charities, whose role it is to inform and advise on the subject; (2) the tourism system's level of responsibility is centred around managing change, through for example creating new knowledge, making adjustments, providing support and developing best practice for transportation and accommodation providers, tour operators, DMOs, visitor attractions, local communities, and other holiday makers; and (3) families (including parents/guardians, neurodivergent children and siblings) themselves are responsible for managing the holiday experience, as well as the challenges and complexities that come with it, through engaging in appropriate family practices and family management strategies. This is not to imply that disabled people should in any way be blamed for the conditions they have. The reality of taking family holidays with neurodivergent members, however, often requires families to compromise and take responsibility for ensuring that the needs and wants of their neurodiverse family are met.

Figure 3. Framework for future research into the responsibility for developing positive holiday experiences for neurodiverse families

Source: Authors

Figure 3 Alt text: shows a framework for future research, it displays three major stakeholders (government, tourism system, and families) who can bring about change through a realisation and actioning of their responsibilities to create positive holiday experiences for neurodivergent children.

One distinct advantage of this framework is that it includes example management strategies at each level of responsibility that will help develop a more holistic understanding of each stakeholder’s role in improving family holidays for neurodivergent children. The framework also allows both a top-down-and-bottom-up approach in order to explore the inter-relatedness of the three levels. For example, neurodiverse families engage in different family practices to cope with the additional challenges while on holiday. A better understanding of family management strategies that work or do not work could help inform the development of best

practices across the tourism-system level of responsibility. This can, in turn, serve to promote change in legislation and policy at the government level of responsibility. This is an example of the bottom-up development of practice.

Practice can also be developed in a top-down manner, for example by governments spreading public awareness of autism and the difficulties of holidaymaking for a neurodiverse family. This will help establish a more positive attitude on the part of other holidaymakers towards neurodiversity and can, in turn, be operationalised by developing awareness programmes at the tourism-system level that are implemented by individual tourism organisations. Neurodiverse families can then adapt their family management strategies accordingly. It is envisaged, then, that the three levels of responsibility mutually reinforce each other. Actors at different levels of the framework can thereby work together to achieve desirable changes in the tourism industry and society as a whole.

Government level of responsibility

Governments, policymakers and third-sector organisations are responsible for making tourism governance ‘fit for purpose’, and it is the tourism policymakers’ responsibility “to take informed decisions and actively engage in the formulation of national strategies in order to strengthen the role of tourism in achieving the SDGs” (UNWTO & UNDP, 2017, p. 29). A first consideration regarding the government level of responsibility therefore relates to the role of governance. This is important as it will ultimately frame and shape the specific tools used by the government, at various levels, to pursue the policy goals they adopt. Governance denotes “a conceptual and theoretical representation of the role of the state in the coordination of socio-economic systems” (Hall, 2011, p. 440). This includes relationships between the state and other

policy actors, as well as the wider network of public-private partnerships. Hall's (2011) framework of governance could be applied to explore and critically investigate different governance structures and how they are related to tourism policy instruments. The key elements of the framework are structured around hierarchies (nation, state and supranational institutions), markets (marketisation and privatisation of state instruments), networks (public-private partnerships), and communities (private-private partnerships and communities). Specific research questions to investigate these structures and the roles they play in the policy process can then be developed (see Table 2). They can be related to the UN Sustainable Development Goals. Specifically, they can be focused on the key proposition that offering universally accessible products and services to reduce inequality (SDG 10) and providing opportunities to help everyone live healthy lives (SD3), are crucial in enhancing their sustainable well-being. The role and responsibility of tourism policymakers in this should be further explored as they can influence institutional mechanisms and take a proactive role when designing and developing action plans for implementing the SDGs.

Secondly, at the government level of responsibility, it is important to recognise that working with charities, NGOs and other third-sector organisations is a crucial part of the policymaking process. The recently published "National Strategy for Autistic Children, Young People and Adults: 2021 to 2026" recognises the importance of collaboration between national and local government, as well as across different government departments in England and with other local partners to take forward the priorities set out in the strategy (Department of Health and Social Care & Department for Education, 2021). Organisations such as the National Autistic Society, to take but one example, also have a key role to play in the process, as they are well placed to understand the needs of autistic people through their important, ongoing work specifically *with* (rather than simply *for*) autistic people.

Casey's (2004) multi-disciplinary framework for analysing third-sector participation in the policy process provides a useful tool to investigate the role of this and similar organisations in developing a better awareness and understanding of neurodiverse conditions in general. It is also particularly important in informing decisions about when and how best to provide support for neurodiverse tourism through policies and legislation. The framework is based on four factors: the political and socioeconomic environment (including dominant political discourses and policy structures); the policy in question (including the nature of the policy conflict and the phase of the policy cycle); the characteristics of the third sector organisation involved (its ideology and culture, membership, status and organisational capacity); and the network of actors. The third-sector organisations' technical and political legitimacy both need to be critically investigated.

Tourism system level of responsibility

While many actors within the tourism system have started to take on the responsibility to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (UNWTO & UNDP, 2017), the tourism industry is currently not offering inclusive products and services to reduce inequality (Goal 10) for neurodivergent consumers. By not doing this, it is denying them opportunities to enhance their well-being (Goal 3) through family holidays and activities. Greater flexibility is required within the tourism system to accommodate neurodivergent holidaymakers and their families at all levels, including website design, transportation, accommodation, and the many other products, services and facilities that are involved in delivering travel and holiday experiences. Current constraints, pressures and willingness – or unwillingness – of actors to make genuine changes thereby need to be taken into account, including economic, social and ethical considerations. A study by Garrod (2021) reported that even in a tourism sector where ethical issues are prominent – ecotourism – disabled tourists are often frustrated by a lack of information on

tourism company websites. Further research is therefore required at the tourism system level of responsibility with regards to co-creating new knowledge between all actors within the tourism network, making necessary adjustments and providing support to neurodiverse families, and developing best practices across the industry.

Future research should also seek to develop specific tools and practices that can help neurodiverse families enjoy their holiday experience more fully. Dempsey et al. (2021), for example, identified a range of key enablers for air travel with autistic children/young adults, such as fast-track systems, priority boarding, pre-selection of seats, and access to a customer service representative prior to the flight. Sensory packs including noise-cancelling headphones to block out unfamiliar noise, could also be used by airlines and accommodation providers to help autistic children adjust to the change in their environment. Such items can help forestall an autistic child having a meltdown, which in turn may prevent disruption for travellers or hotel guests and the negative social interactions this may lead to. Similarly, virtual reality could be used to create online resources for neurodivergent travellers to be able to ‘look around’ the vehicle they are to be travelling in or the hotel room in which they are to be staying. Making such resources available for neurodiverse customers is best considered the main responsibility of the service providers. While governments can raise awareness, and families can purchase and bring the resources, it is often only in the transit region or the destination that the need for them becomes apparent. Travellers often also have tight luggage limits, making it impossible for them to bring a range of bulky and easily damaged equipment. Further research is also needed into how such technology can be designed to assist neurodivergent customers of different provider organisations.

Lastly, a key task of further research into neurodiversity at the tourism system level should be to identify the content and delivery methods needed to provide appropriate training for ‘frontline’ staff across all sectors with regard to neurodiverse conditions. A key challenge for neurodiverse families discussed in this paper is the lack of support available during holidays, and staff who can demonstrate empathy, understanding and sufficient flexibility to provide solutions to the challenges and complexities experienced by neurodiverse holidaymakers, can arguably make a difference here. While governments might be able to encourage such training, and even support organisations to train their employees by providing programmes, short courses, learning resources or grants to help individuals access such training, the responsibility is ultimately that of the tourism provider organisations to train their staff, the majority of which is based in the private and third sectors of the economy. There are, however, two particular challenges in the tourism and hospitality context. The first is staff turnover, which tends to be relatively high, and often makes employers reluctant to provide ‘too much’ training to their recruits. The second is the frequent lack of clear career-development paths, which makes it less likely that staff will wish to undergo additional training once they have been trained in the basics. A similar problem exists with regard to the development of green or sustainable-development training in the tourism and hospitality industry, and some organisations have responded by appointing ‘champions’ within their workforce to promote such issues at the ‘grassroots’ level (Sullivan, 2017). This may be an approach that can be easily transferred to accessibility for disabled people in general, and neurodivergent customers in particular. More research is needed, however, to establish how best to achieve this and further potential questions for future research at this level of responsibility are outlined in Table 2.

Neurodiverse family level of responsibility

Undeniably, parents and guardians of neurodivergent children also have a responsibility when it comes to planning a family holiday, as well as during the holiday itself and when returning from the holiday (Jepson et al, 2022). Rather than merely investigating the many challenges neurodiverse families face when going on holiday, future research at this level of responsibility should also explore the practices neurodiverse families engage in while on holiday and how they are different to their day-to-day family practices. This will allow a better understanding of how neurodiverse families can benefit from holiday experiences and memories, including family functioning and bonding, personal as well as family growth in the short, medium and longer term. One potential concept to apply when exploring these practices, is that of family management strategies or styles (FMS).

At the family level, FMSs have previously been used to identify patterns and typologies of a family's response to specific healthcare challenges. In their study of families with children with ADHD, Kendall and Shelton (2003) identified four specific FMS and developed recommendations for each: the chaotic family is defined as an extremely stressed family with limited support internally or externally for children and parents, and the parents are not responding to the emotional needs of their children. The ADHD-controlled family is characterised by a negative view of the future (nothing will change), reinforced by child hegemony over parents' (through the child's care needs); in this type of family, the family life revolves around the child's condition and family functioning is defined by moments of havoc, crises, and exhaustion. Thirdly, the surviving family is a family that actively seeks ways of living successfully with their child's condition, where ADHD is a key part of family life, but this type of family recognises the importance of dealing with individual family member needs and the other emotional aspects of family life. There is an increased emotional involvement between family members who work together and learn how to create a family centred home rather than one which is dominated by ADHD. Lastly, the reinvested family is a family that

has undergone a process of family functioning development from survival to ‘reinvesting’ their energy into themselves (and taken back control of their lives), into one another, and into family life while the condition of ADHD functions in the background. Here, family members accept that ADHD is a lifelong condition, and there is therefore greater emphasis on the child with ADHD to face their problems and find ways to move forward, rather than parents or family members seeking solutions for them.

Arguably, different families will use different family practices and FMSs at different times in their daily lives. Research into FMS is, however, currently limited in respect of holidays and changing environments, and should be an area of future research into tourism and neurodiversity. As previously noted, the challenges experienced while on holiday affect the family as a whole. Rather than merely focusing on these challenges, researchers should seek to understand how family practices may enable the co-creation of positive and enriching holiday experiences. For example, drawing on the wider family sociology literature may help address the question of whether a positive holiday memory shared by all members of the family could potentially help a ‘surviving’ family transition to become a ‘reinvested’ one. Further research questions that need to be considered at this level of responsibility are outlined in Table 2.

Future research

It is time for researchers to be mindful of neurodiversity when they research and to apply a more critical lens to neurodiversity in tourism. This paper therefore concludes with a call to action for researchers to apply the above framework to explore the different holiday experiences of neurodiverse families through multi- and interdisciplinary approaches and to develop a more holistic perspective. In adopting the framework, the authors encourage researchers to be mindful of their contributions and to avoid the desire to create generalised

findings as these may prove to be inappropriate to neurodiverse populations as a result of the heterogeneous nature of neurodiversity and neurodiverse conditions. As outlined at the beginning of the paper, different models and thought paradigms of neurodiversity exist. Researchers undertaking studies into neurodiversity should therefore seek to identify their positionality with respect to how this informs and influences their research with neurodiverse populations. Longitudinal studies, and those that are conducted *with* rather than *on* neurodiverse families, are recommended. Such research practices will allow parents', guardians' as well as neurodivergent children's voices to be better heard, so that researchers can understand their needs and wants for different holiday experiences, as well as to explore challenges and changes over time.

Furthermore, tourism researchers should focus on a deeper and more meaningful debate into the complexities and challenges of neurodiversity and the moral responsibilities of the tourism industry and governments to specifically address these. It is important to understand how and why neurodivergent people come to be marginalised when taking a holiday, and to clarify where the responsibilities of a family with neurodivergent children end, and those of the tourism industry begin (Jepson et al., 2022). For example, if an autistic child has associated sleep complications while on holiday, it might be unreasonable to expect parents to pack blackout curtains in their already full suitcases. Despite recent trends in the tourism industry and governments to take on opportunities and responsibilities to achieve the SDGs, the tourism industry still too often uses purely economic arguments (such as the loss of revenue from accessible hotel rooms, as neurotypicals often refuse to use them), and from a standpoint of not being able to assist all disabilities/non-neurotypical conditions.

Table 2 illustrates a number of potential questions emanating from this paper that could be taken forward by tourism researchers to make contributions to knowledge within the field of

tourism and neurodiversity, with a particular emphasis on the three levels of responsibility discussed in this section. The proposed questions focus on neurodiverse families in general but can easily be adapted to investigate any of the neurodiverse conditions (see Figure 1), as well as the differences between them.

Level of responsibility	Research questions	Informed by
Government	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do different governance structures enhance / inhibit the development of tourism policies that ensure equal opportunities for neurodiverse families to exercise their human rights and benefit from family holidays in the same ways as neurotypical families do? - What is the role of third sector organisations and public-private partnerships in developing inclusive products and services for the tourism industry to reduce inequality? - How do governments embrace the goals of the social model of neurodiversity when developing tourism policy, legislation and guidance? 	Hall (2011); Department of Health and Social Care & Department for Education (2021); Casey (2004); UNWTO & UNDP (2017)
Tourism system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How are neurodiverse families treated by tourism industry organisations on their holidays in comparison to neurotypical families, and how does this affect them socially, physiologically and psychologically? - How fit-for-purpose are sectors of the tourism industry in respect to responding to the challenges and complexities of supporting neurodiverse families to have positive experiences and happy holidays? - What best practice/ support is currently available within the tourism system to widen accessibility for neurodiverse people and make holidays more inclusive? - How can existing positive practices be adapted, enhanced and/or shared across the tourism system so that they better contribute towards meeting the needs of neurodiverse families on holiday? - What training schemes exist to support employees on the ‘frontline’ to ensure they can support neurodiverse people? - How can employees be trained/ educated differently to ensure they understand the needs of neurodiverse people and are flexible to problem solving? 	UNWTO & UNDP (2017); Garrod (2021); Dempsey et al. (2021); Robertson (2010); Sullivan (2017)
Neurodiverse families	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do neurodiverse families benefit from holiday experiences and memories, such as family functioning, bonding, identity, personal/family growth in the short, medium, and longer term? - What practices do neurodiverse families engage in while on holiday and how are they different to their day-to-day family practices? 	Jepson et al. (2022); Kendall & Shelton (2003)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What family management strategies / styles do neurodiverse families use to deal with the complexities and challenges encountered on holiday? 	
Across all 3 levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do decisions at different levels of responsibility impact upon neurodivergent children’s holiday experiences? - What level of understanding and awareness is required from governments, tourism stakeholders and other holidaymakers to enhance a neurodiverse family’s holiday experience? - How do family holidays benefit neurodivergent, and neurotypical family members in the short/medium and longer term contributing to members’ independence, yet also family bonding and cohesiveness and positive functioning? <p>TOP-DOWN:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can a better understanding and awareness of neurodiversity in society help develop best practices across the tourism system? - What type of support and adjustments across the tourism system are most beneficial for neurodiverse families to effectively manage their holiday experiences? <p>BOTTOM-UP:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How can effective family management strategies used by neurodiverse families on holiday help create new knowledge for the tourism system? - How can neurodiverse families inform and advise sectors within the tourism system to improve their staff training and the level of support for neurodiverse holidaymakers? - How can neurodiverse families and charities co-create holiday experiences to inform and advise local, regional and national governments? - What is the role of inclusive tourism best practices in the policy-making process at the local and national government level? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opportunities to contribute to tourism knowledge

Table 2. Questions for future research at and across different levels of responsibility and opportunities to contribute to tourism knowledge

Table 2 Alt text: Table 2 builds on figure 3 and sets out examples of research questions for each major stakeholder (governments, tourism system, neurodiverse families). Table 2 also includes questions that should be adopted by all of the stakeholders

Conclusions and Limitations

It has been documented here that the tourism industry has mainly been focused upon neurotypical populations and traditional family composition. It is ultimately the case that research outcomes are partly a product of the researchers themselves and if they are neurotypical then the knock-on effect of this might be research outcomes and contributions to knowledge that are only beneficial to neurotypical populations. Before embarking on research into tourism and neurodiversity, researchers should therefore examine the wider neurodiversity discourse in order to position themselves and their study along the medical – social model continuum, acknowledge their potential biases, and critically reflect on their methods and research approaches. This should include questions around the language they use, their ethics of care, as well as inclusion and equity of participation.

This paper has contributed to tourism knowledge by presenting a critical analysis of the oppositionality associated with the medical and social models of disabilities when applied to neurodiversity and concludes that neurodiversity is poorly problematised within the tourism literature. The paper has applied the social model using the example of neurodiversity and in particular to expose the complexities and the challenges involved in holidaymaking faced by families with children who are autistic. This paper has demonstrated that the social model fails to identify what changes are required and who should have responsibility for effecting them. As such, the social model still merely serves the needs of neurotypical holidaymakers. A framework for action was developed through this paper that identifies three tiers of responsibility (governments, the tourism system, neurodiverse families), based on which a proposed research agenda for the future study of tourism and neurodiversity with particular reference to these levels of responsibility was critically identified. A major advantage of this framework is the inter-relatedness of the three levels of responsibility and the top-down-and-

bottom-up approach recommended in the paper which can be used to gain a more holistic understanding of each stakeholder's role in improving family holidays for neurodivergent children.

The paper thus concludes firstly by reiterating that in order to achieve tourism-related SDGs through offering inclusive products and services, reducing inequality and providing neurodivergent consumers opportunities to enhance their well-being through family holidays, the responsibility for supporting neurodiverse families on holiday must be shared equitably by governments, the tourism system, and the families themselves. Deep ethical concerns have been raised throughout this paper in relation to neurodivergent consumers and their rights to fair and equitable treatment while on holiday. This means they have the same opportunities as neurotypical consumers to have positive holiday experiences, memories and the chance to bond with their families. Attention has also been drawn to the conflict that exists between these rights and those parts of the tourism industry that are currently not offering accessible products and services to reduce inequality and by doing this are denying neurodivergent consumers opportunities to benefit from their family holidays and activities in the same way as neurotypical families. The paper therefore further extends the body of knowledge and growing academic literature around issues of accessibility, disability and inclusivity in the tourism context.

Secondly, the magnitude of the complexities and challenges associated with neurodiversity in family holidaymaking has been revealed, and these have been presented using autism as a specific case to demonstrate the support needed from governments, the tourism system and neurodiverse families. In understanding the complexity of neurodiversity as a field of study in the context of tourism, it can be concluded that while each child and family is different, and

each holiday is unique, there is sufficient homogeneity to allow for best practices to be developed. It is important for tourism researchers to break away from the monopoly of neurotypical research, be more critical in their research approaches and be mindful of neurodivergent holidaymakers when putting forward recommendations.

Limitations to the approach taken in this paper are acknowledged. None of the specific management strategies suggested in the framework have yet been tested. Hence there is currently a limited foundation for future research into neurodiversity in tourism. Table 2 therefore proposes some theoretical and practical questions researchers will need to integrate into their studies in order to make contributions to knowledge that can benefit neurodivergent people and the tourism industry more broadly. The question of responsibility and flexibility is incontrovertibly a tourism management issue, and there is a clear and urgent need for the tourism industry to become more flexible and address the levels of responsibility for neurodivergent people. There is also a clear and important need for researchers to be more reflexive in their approach to understanding neurodiverse populations and contributing to knowledge in order that an equity of holiday experience becomes a reality. Only then can more positive holiday experiences for neurodivergent children and their families become a reality.

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